

Suspension of Legislators: Legislative Autonomy and the Limits of Suspension Powers

Mohammed Onyilokwu Amali, PhD¹ & Shalom Danlami Andemi.²

¹Senior Research Fellow,
National Institute for Legislative and Democratic Studies,
(National Assembly), Abuja.

Corresponding author. Email: amalimoh@yahoo.com

²Legal Practitioner and Managing Partner,
S. D. Andemi and Associates (Adonai Chambers),
Abuja, Nigeria.

Email: andemidashalom@gmail.com

Abstract:

The suspension of legislators by their respective legislatures remain one of the most contested intersections between legislative autonomy and democratic accountability. While the power to discipline members is inherent in the legislature's right to regulate its internal affairs, its exercise often raises profound constitutional and democratic questions. This article examines the delicate balance between legislative autonomy, democratic representation, and the limits of suspension powers with particular reference to the Nigerian experience and comparative commonwealth jurisdictions. Drawing from constitutional provisions, judicial precedents, and normative democratic theory, the paper argues that the suspension power, although justifiable on grounds such as maintenance of order, protection of institutional integrity, and enforcement of ethical standards, must operate within the boundaries of proportionality, fairness, and respect for the right of representation. Unchecked autonomy, the paper contends, produces a paradox of the legislature's quest to preserve its independence which may, in practice, subvert the very principles of representation and accountability upon which its legitimacy rests. The paper finds that the true measure of a legislature's autonomy lies not in its immunity from review, but in its fidelity to democratic values, constitutional restraint, and the enduring right of the people to be represented through their elected voices. The paper recommends clearer procedural safeguards, and codified disciplinary frameworks in order to prevent abuse.

Keywords: Constitutionalism, Democratic Representation, Legislative Accountability, Legislative Autonomy, Parliamentary Privilege, Suspension Powers.

Suggested Citation: M. O. Amali & S. D. Andemi (2025), 'Suspension of Legislators: Legislative Autonomy and the Limits of Suspension Powers,' *East. Af. JLP&G*. Vol. 4. No.1. pp. 1-27.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution
International License (CC BY 4.0).

1. INTRODUCTION

The legislature occupies a central place in any democratic system as the institutional embodiment of the people's sovereignty and representation. Through oversight, law-making, and representation, the legislature gives expression to the collective will and ensures accountability within the constitutional order. However, the autonomy of the legislature remains one of the most contested features of constitutional democracy, particularly in emerging political systems because the question of suspension powers within internal parliamentary leadership strikes at the very heart of legislative independence. While temporary suspensions may be justified under exceptional circumstances, i.e. gross misconduct, the abuse or arbitrary use of such powers undermine the principle of democratic representation. This is due to lack of political will, which has become a common feature of Nigeria's governance architecture. It must be noted that such declarations are from courts of first instance, and the Supreme Court has not had the opportunity of making pronouncements on these cases. In several jurisdictions, this tension has generated significant constitutional and political debates on the proper limits of such authority.¹

Within the Nigerian context, the issue of suspension powers has surfaced repeatedly within the National and State Houses of Assembly. Instances where presiding officers or dominant majorities have suspended members, often for dissenting views, political rivalry, or alleged misconduct, have sparked public debate on the boundaries of internal legislative authority. This frequent resort to suspension of legislators, often without clear procedural safeguards, has raised fundamental questions about the limits of internal parliamentary authority and the protection of democratic representation. Suspensions have, in several cases, seemingly been used not merely as disciplinary measures, but as instruments of political control, effectively silencing dissent and excluding constituencies from participation in governance. This practice undermines the representative mandate of elected members and weakens public confidence in the legislature as a democratic institution.

While the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as altered) grants each legislative house the power to regulate its own procedure,² courts have increasingly been called upon to determine whether such powers extend to suspending elected representatives. These controversies highlight a persistent constitutional tension between maintaining legislative discipline and protecting the electorate's right to representation. The Constitution is also silent on the scope and duration of sanctions that may be imposed on members. The resulting ambiguity has created space for conflicting interpretations, institutional overreach, and judicial intervention. Instructively, courts have occasionally declared such suspensions unconstitutional, emphasising that no House Rule can

¹ The jurisdictions of India, Nigeria, South Africa and the United Kingdom will be scrutinised in this paper.

² Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (As Altered), s.60

override the electorate's right to continuous representation.³ Nevertheless, the persistence of these incidents suggests deeper structural and normative gaps in Nigeria's legislative governance.

This paper situates its analysis within recurring Nigerian experiences to illustrate how unchecked suspension powers can erode democratic representation and weaken the very autonomy the legislature seeks to protect. The paper interrogates the relationship between legislative autonomy, democratic representation, and the legal and constitutional limits of suspension powers. This study therefore seeks to examine the constitutional and legal foundations of legislative autonomy in Nigeria by analysing the scope and limitations of the suspension powers exercised within the Nigerian legislature. Drawing from comparative insights from other democratic systems on balancing internal legislative discipline with members' representational rights, the paper evaluates the implications of such powers for democratic representation and separation of powers. By addressing these objectives, the paper aims to contribute to the ongoing discourse on constitutionalism, legislative governance, and the protection of representative democracy in Nigeria.

The paper is discussed in six sections. Following this introductory section, section 2 clarifies key concepts that shall be used in the course of the paper. Section 3 undertakes a cross-jurisdictional review of parliamentary rules, while section 4 analyses the justifications for legislative houses suspending elected legislators. Section 5 discusses the findings, and recommendations, with section 6 being the conclusion.

2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Legislative autonomy

The word 'legislative autonomy' is a combination of two independent concepts- 'legislative' and 'autonomy'. To understand this concept properly therefore, this paper describes what the two independent words are before considering them as a whole. The word 'legislative' relates to laws or the making of laws.⁴ On the other hand, 'autonomy' has been described to mean "the legally entrenched power of communities to exercise public policy functions of a legislative, executive and, or judicial type independently of other sources of authority in the state, but subject to the overall legal order of the state."⁵ Taken together, Legislative Autonomy refers to the constitutionally recognised freedom of a legislative body to regulate its internal affairs and procedures independently, without undue interference from the executive or judiciary, provided such independence is exercised within the bounds of constitutional supremacy.

³ *The President of the Senate of The FRN & Ors v Ndume* (2022) LPELR-57712(CA).

⁴ Cambridge Dictionary, Meaning of Legislative in English <<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/legislative>> accessed 15 September, 2025.

⁵ Stefan Wolff, Autonomy <<https://pesd.princeton.edu/node/236>> accessed 15 September, 2025.

2.2 Democratic representation

Democratic representation is a political concept also referred to as indirect democracy or representative government.⁶ It is a form of democracy based on the principle that elected officials act on behalf of the people, in contrast to direct democracy, where citizens participate personally in decision-making.⁷ Representation is indispensable in any democratic constitution because it is through representatives that government can meaningfully claim to be “by the people.”⁸ The very essence of representative democracy lies in the fact that the will of the people is fulfilled through representative bodies directly elected by the citizens themselves.⁹

Historically, “representative democracy has gone through stages of its development, which were neither easy nor quick. With the creation of large nation-states, whereby it could not be governed through forms of direct democracy, representation became a necessity, without any alternative.¹⁰ John Stuart Mill as a proponent of representative democracy focused mainly on how to ensure efficient government and respect for personal rights and freedoms, whereas Charles Louis de Montesquieu created ideas on democracies, which are still characteristic of modern democracies.”¹¹ Montesquieu spread the idea of a representative democracy, whereby the people would elect their own representatives to make decisions and promulgate laws.¹² These foundational ideas continue to underpin the principle of democratic representation in contemporary constitutional practice.

2.3 Suspension of powers

The phrase suspension of powers is a compound of two concepts- ‘suspension’, and ‘power’. Suspension refers to the act of temporarily delaying, interrupting, or terminating something.¹³ It also denotes the state of such delay or deprivation. Within legal and institutional contexts, suspension often implies the temporary removal of a person’s powers, functions, or privileges, especially in relation to an office or profession.¹⁴ Power, by contrast, has been defined as the amount of political control a person or group wields

⁶ World Economic Forum, Democratic Representation <<https://intelligence.weforum.org/topics/e102519ccf5140ee9941206b3713f2a0>> accessed 15 September, 2025.

⁷ *ibid.*

⁸ Philip Pettit, Varieties of Public Representation <www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&opi=89978449&url=http://www.lecre.umontreal.ca/wp-content/uploads/2008/10/Varieties_of_Public_RepresentationPettitSept08.doc&ved=2ahUKEwiLzuSz0NqPAXUeWUEAHUC8D7cQFnoECDUQAQ&usq=AOvVaw0OPYhdozARKQkV0SkZEqe4> accessed 15 September, 2025.

⁹ Sadik Haxhiu and Avni H. Alidemaj, Representative Democracy – Its Meaning and Basic Concepts <<https://dj.univ-danubius.ro/index.php/AUDJ/article/view/1253/1447>> accessed 16 September, 2025.

¹⁰ *ibid.*

¹¹ *ibid.*

¹² *ibid.*

¹³ Bryan A. Garner, *The Black’s Law Dictionary*, 8th Edition; *Miaphen v Unijos Consultancy Ltd* (2013) LPELR-2190 29-30 (CA).

¹⁴ *Okoronkwo v. INEC* (2025) LPELR-80425 15-16 (SC).

within a state.¹⁵ Taken together, suspension of powers means the temporary withdrawal or curtailment of the authority, rights, or privileges vested in an officeholder, particularly an elected legislator, as a disciplinary or regulatory measure.

In the legislative context, suspension of powers functions as a disciplinary mechanism against legislators, aimed at preserving order, integrity, and decorum within parliamentary chambers. However, because such suspension simultaneously deprives a constituency of representation, it must be exercised cautiously and within constitutional boundaries, ensuring that discipline does not translate into disenfranchisement.

2.4 Suspension, expulsion, recall, and disqualification

In this section, this paper distinguishes between these concepts that are sometimes mistakenly conflated.

2.4.1 Suspension

As earlier defined, suspension is the temporary removal of a person's powers, functions, or privileges, especially in relation to an office or profession.¹⁶ In legislative practice, suspension is a disciplinary mechanism to maintain order, decorum, and integrity within the chamber.¹⁷ Its defining feature is its temporary character, because once the suspension lapses, the legislator resumes full functions.

2.4.2 Expulsion

By contrast, this is a more severe sanction. It is often considered a matter of institutional self-protection, aimed at safeguarding the integrity of the legislature and its proceedings.¹⁸ Expulsion is the act of being forced out or made to leave an institution permanently, effectively terminating one's membership in the legislative body.¹⁹ Unlike suspension, expulsion permanently deprives a legislator and their constituents of representation unless a by-election is held.

2.4.3 Recall

This differs fundamentally because it is a popular, not parliamentary, mechanism. It is a constitutionally provided process through which citizens may remove an elected legislator from office before the expiration of his or her term²⁰. It is a process through which a

¹⁵Cambridge Dictionary, Meaning of Power in English <<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/power>> accessed 16 September, 2025.

¹⁶ *Okoronkwo* (n 13).

¹⁷ Legislative Houses (Powers and Privileges) Act, 2017, ss 14(2) and 15.

¹⁸ Jack Maskell, Expulsion, Censure, Reprimand, and Fine: Legislative Discipline in the House of Representatives <<https://sgp.fas.org/crs/misc/RL31382.pdf>> accessed 16 September, 2025.

¹⁹ Collins Dictionary, Expulsion <www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/expulsion> accessed 16 September, 2025.

²⁰ Halima Adeosun, 'How constituents in Nigeria can recall underperforming legislators [Explainer]' *TheRader* (Nigeria, 15 November, 2024) <[TheRader - How constituents in Nigeria can recall underperforming legislators \[Explainer\]](https://www.therader.com/2024/11/15/how-constituents-in-nigeria-can-recall-underperforming-legislators-explainer/)> accessed 16 September, 2025.

validly elected lawmaker may be removed from his or her seat in the Senate, House of Representatives and House of Assembly.²¹ Recall thus embodies direct democratic accountability, in contrast to suspension or expulsion, which are internal legislative measures.

2.4.4 Disqualification

This refers to a legal bar that prevents a person from contesting or holding office in the first place. It has been defined as the act of stopping someone from taking part in a competition or activity, usually because a rule has been broken.²² Within the constitutional context, disqualification may arise from grounds such as conviction for certain offences, bankruptcy, unsoundness of mind, or failure to meet age and educational requirements.²³ Unlike suspension or expulsion, disqualification operates as a preventive measure.

Put together, these four concepts highlight different mechanisms of accountability and discipline. Suspension is temporary and internal, expulsion is permanent and internal, recall is permanent and external, driven by constituents, while disqualification is preventive, barring eligibility to hold office in the first place. While they may appear similar in effect, that is, the removal or restriction of legislative authority, these concepts differ substantially in nature, process, and constitutional foundation.

3. STANDING ORDERS AND PARLIAMENTARY RULES: A CROSS-JURISDICTIONAL ANALYSIS

3.1 Parliamentary privilege as a historical justification

The idea of legislative autonomy has deep historical roots in the doctrine of parliamentary privilege, which originated in the Westminster model and has since influenced many constitutional democracies.²⁴ Parliamentary privilege refers to the special rights and immunities enjoyed by legislatures and their members, enabling them to perform their functions independently and without fear of external interference.²⁵

²¹ Nafisat Bello, 'What You Need to Know About Recalling a Lawmaker in Nigeria' *PRNigeria* (Nigeria, Friday 28 March, 2025) <What you Need to Know About Recalling a Lawmaker in Nigeria - PRNigeria News> accessed 16 September, 2025; 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, ss 69 and 110.

²² Cambridge Dictionary, Meaning of Disqualification in English <DISQUALIFICATION | English meaning - Cambridge Dictionary> accessed 16 September, 2025.

²³ 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, ss 66 and 137; *Edeoga & Anor v INEC & Ors* (2023) LPELR-61806 65-(SC); *Rhodes-Vivour v INEC & Ors* (2024) LPELR-63003 54-55 (SC); *Aminu & Anor v INEC & Ors* (2024) LPELR-61787 15-20 (SC).

²⁴ House of Commons Procedure and Practice, 'Privileges and Immunities' <www.ourcommons.ca/marleaumontpetit/DocumentViewer.aspx?Language=E&Sec=Ch03&Seq=3> accessed 21 September, 2025.

²⁵ *ibid.*

In the United Kingdom, parliamentary privilege was famously entrenched in Article 9 of the Bill of Rights 1689,²⁶ which provides that “the freedom of speech and debates or proceedings in Parliament ought not to be impeached or questioned in any court or place out of Parliament.” This provision was a response to earlier conflicts between Parliament and the Crown, and it remains the cornerstone of legislative independence in the UK.²⁷ Judicial authority has reinforced this principle, as seen in *Bradlaugh v Gossett*,²⁸ where the court held that it had no jurisdiction to interfere in parliamentary proceedings.

In Nigeria, the doctrine of parliamentary privilege was inherited through colonial constitutional practice and later codified in the Legislative Houses (Powers and Privileges) Act.²⁹ This Act grants members of the National Assembly and State Houses of Assembly privileges such as immunity from legal action for words spoken in legislative proceedings, and protection from arrest in civil matters while the legislature is in session.³⁰ These privileges mirror the Westminster tradition³¹ and serve to preserve legislative independence within the framework of the Nigerian Constitution.

In India, parliamentary privilege is recognised both by constitutional text and by convention. Articles 105 and 194 of the Constitution³² grant privileges to Parliament and State Legislatures, respectively, including freedom of speech in the legislature and immunity for publication of proceedings. The Supreme Court has interpreted these privileges as essential to legislative independence but has consistently maintained that they remain subject to constitutional supremacy.³³

In South Africa, parliamentary privilege is also expressly embedded in the Constitution. Section 58³⁴ provides that “Cabinet members, Deputy Ministers and members of the National Assembly have freedom of speech in the Assembly and its committees, subject to its rules and orders.” Similar provisions apply to the National Council of Provinces under Section 71. These privileges, although constitutionally protected, are expressly framed to operate within the democratic values of accountability and transparency.

Historically, therefore, parliamentary privilege has served as a justification for legislative autonomy, protecting legislatures from undue interference and enabling them

²⁶Erskine May, UK Parliament, Bill of Rights, a IX<<https://erskinemay.parliament.uk/section/4589/article-ix-of-the-bill-of-rights>> accessed 20th September, 2025.

²⁷ <www.parliament.gov.za/storage/app/media/Rules/NCOP/Rules_of_NCOP_9th_edition.pdf> accessed 21 September, 2025.

²⁸ [1884] EWHC 1 (QB).

²⁹ 1953; 2017.

³⁰ Legislative Houses (Powers and Privileges) Act, 2017, s 1.

³¹ Legislative Assembly of British Columbia, The Westminster Tradition <www.leg.bc.ca/learn/discover-your-legislature/constitutional-framework-governance/westminster-tradition> accessed 21 September, 2025.

³² Legislative Department, The Constitution of India, 2024 <https://legislative.gov.in/constitution-of-india/>> accessed 20 September, 2025.

³³ *Raja Ram Pal v Hon'ble Speaker, Lok Sabha* (2007).

³⁴ Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996 www.justice.gov.za/constitution/SACConstitution-web-eng.pdf> accessed 20 September, 2025.

to perform their law-making and oversight functions effectively. Across jurisdictions, however, its scope has evolved from an almost absolute shield against judicial intervention (as partly, in the UK) to a balanced doctrine where autonomy exists but is constrained by constitutional supremacy (as in Nigeria, India, and South Africa).

3.2 The doctrinal roots: separation of powers and institutional independence

The doctrine of separation of powers provides the most fundamental justification for legislative autonomy.³⁵ Rooted in the writings of Charles Louis de Montesquieu in “The Spirit of Laws”, the actual practice of separation of powers amongst different branches of government can be traced to ancient Greece.³⁶ The principle posits that governmental power should be divided among the legislature, the executive, and the judiciary, in order to prevent the concentration of authority in a single branch. Each arm of government must therefore enjoy a degree of institutional independence sufficient to carry out its functions effectively.³⁷ In the legislative context, autonomy in regulating internal proceedings is a natural extension of this doctrine. If the executive or the judiciary were permitted to dictate how a legislature conducts its business, the balance of power carefully designed by constitutional frameworks would be distorted.³⁸ Autonomy therefore ensures that legislatures can exercise their core functions free from undue interference.

In Nigeria, this doctrinal basis is reflected in the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999, specifically section 4 (which vests legislative powers in the National Assembly) and section 60 (which empowers each House to regulate its procedure). Similarly, in India, Articles 118 and 208 of the Constitution of India, 2024, embody the same principle, while in South Africa, sections 57 and 70 Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996, confer comparable authority. Even in the United Kingdom, where no codified constitution exists, parliamentary privilege has historically served to insulate parliament from royal and judicial interference, reinforcing institutional independence. All these notwithstanding, separation of powers does not imply absolute insulation because the judiciary still retains the role of constitutional guardians, empowered to review legislative actions when they conflict with constitutional supremacy or fundamental rights. Thus, institutional independence is balanced by constitutional accountability, ensuring that autonomy does not degenerate into arbitrariness.

³⁵ Anyim-Ben, Francisca. O., Okereke, Samuel. N., and Chijioko, Ngozi ‘The Doctrine of Separation of Powers and Checks and Balances in the Nigerian Executive-Legislative Relationship’ (2017) (9) (1) Nnamdi Azikiwe Journal of Philosophy <www.journals.ezenwaohaetorc.org/index.php/NAJP/article/viewFile/9-1-2017-007/193> accessed 21 September, 2025.

³⁶ *ibid.*

³⁷ *ibid.*

³⁸ *ibid.*

3.3 Constitutional basis of legislative autonomy

A legislature's claim to autonomy derives first and foremost from express constitutional provisions which empowers it to regulate its internal proceedings and safeguard its institutional independence.³⁹ While the precise wording and scope of these provisions differ across jurisdictions, they share a common purpose, which is to insulate legislative bodies from undue interference by the executive and judiciary, thereby preserving the doctrine of separation of powers. In Nigeria, the United Kingdom, South Africa, and India, constitutional texts (or their functional equivalents) recognise this autonomy, even if the courts later interpret them in varying ways. Importantly, while constitutions provide the overarching legal framework for legislative autonomy, the actual regulation of parliamentary proceedings is carried out through Standing Orders⁴⁰ and Rules of Procedure adopted by legislative houses. These instruments derive their authority from constitutional provisions, but function as the operational blueprint for legislative business.

An understanding of these provisions within the context of selected jurisdictions is therefore essential, since they form the legal foundation upon which judicial review of legislative discipline shall be discussed in the course of this paper.

3.3.1 Nigeria

The constitutional foundation of legislative autonomy in Nigeria is explicitly stated in Section 60 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria⁴¹, which empowers the Senate and the House of Representatives to “regulate their own procedure, including the procedure for summoning and recess of the House.” Section 101 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria⁴² provides a similar power to the State Houses of Assembly, thus entrenching legislative independence at both the federal and state levels. This autonomy is absolute in relation to regulating internal activities, although, like in other jurisdictions, it remains subject to the overarching principle of constitutional supremacy.⁴³

This constitutional power has necessitated the enactment of detailed Standing Orders, such as the Senate Standing Orders 2023 (as amended), that governs the day-to-day functioning of the senate. Since legislative chambers derive their authority to enact Standing Orders directly from the Constitution, these rules are constitutionally valid. However, they do not override the Constitution itself. In practice, the Standing Orders regulate matters such as order of business, conduct of debates, and disciplinary measures,

³⁹ 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (As Altered), s 60.

⁴⁰ Thomson Reuters, Standing Orders [https://uk.practicallaw.thomsonreuters.com/4-385-1401?transitionType=Default&contextData=\(sc.Default\)>](https://uk.practicallaw.thomsonreuters.com/4-385-1401?transitionType=Default&contextData=(sc.Default)>) accessed 20 September, 2025.

⁴¹ Subject to the provisions of this Constitution, the Senate or the House of Representatives shall have power to regulate its own procedure, including the procedure for summoning and recess of the House.

⁴² Subject to the provisions of this Constitution, a House of Assembly shall have power to regulate its own procedure, including the procedure for summoning and recess of the House; *Musa & Anor v. Basiru & Ors* (2023) LPELR-61577(CA).

⁴³ 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (As Altered), s 1(3).

while also addressing issues relating to members' privileges and the mechanisms for enforcing them when disputes arise.⁴⁴

3.3.2 The United Kingdom

Unlike jurisdictions such as Nigeria, India, and South Africa, which expressly entrench legislative autonomy in their written constitutions, the United Kingdom does not operate under a single codified constitution.⁴⁵ Instead, its constitutional order is derived from statutes, conventions, and judicial decisions.⁴⁶ Within this framework, the principle of legislative autonomy finds expression primarily in the doctrine of parliamentary privilege, the most authoritative source of which is Article 9 of the Bill of Rights 1689.⁴⁷ This provision insulates parliamentary proceedings from judicial interference by affirming that the "freedom of speech and debates or proceedings in parliament ought not to be impeached or questioned in any court or place out of parliament."⁴⁸ They regulate the conduct of debates, questions of order, voting, and disciplinary processes within each House. Although flexible and amendable by parliament itself, the Standing Orders carry constitutional weight in practice, as courts traditionally refrain from questioning their validity or interfering in parliamentary proceedings.⁴⁹ Thus, within the context of the United Kingdom, Standing Orders are an essential expression of legislative autonomy within an uncodified constitutional framework.

In what may be seen as an exception to the general principle in the UK for the judiciary not to interfere in parliamentary affairs however, the UK Supreme Court in September 2019 ruled on two questions regarding an Order to prorogue the UK Parliament.⁵⁰ First, was it justiciable, in other words, could the decision to prorogue be subjected to scrutiny by the courts? Second, was it legal? By way of background, at a meeting of the Privy Council, Her Majesty, the Queen, by Order in Council, ordered that Parliament be prorogued. The prorogation was to take effect on a day between 9th and 12th of September. Parliament was to be summoned again on the 14th of October for a new session. Her Majesty was acting on the advice of her Prime Minister. Parliament was then

⁴⁴ Senate Standing Orders 2023 As Amended, chap IV.

⁴⁵ The Constitution Society, The UK Constitution <<https://consoc.org.uk/the-constitution-explained/the-uk-constitution/>> accessed 20 September, 2025.

⁴⁶ *ibid.*

⁴⁷ Erskine May, UK Parliament, Bill of Rights, art IX <<https://erskinemay.parliament.uk/section/4589/article-ix-of-the-bill-of-rights>> accessed 20 September, 2025.

⁴⁸ English Bill of Rights, 1689, art 9 <<https://users.ssc.wisc.edu/~rkeyser/wp/wp-content/uploads/2015/06/English-Bill-of-Rights1.pdf>> accessed 20 September, 2025.

⁴⁹ *Bradlaugh v Gossett* [1884] EWHC 1 (QB) <www.casemine.com/judgement/uk/5a938b4160d03e5f6b82bd74> accessed 20 September, 2025.

⁵⁰ Decision of the Supreme Court on the Prorogation of Parliament: Published Tuesday, 24 September, 2019 <<https://commonslibrary.parliament.uk/decision-of-the-supreme-court-on-the-prorogation-of-parliament/>> accessed 24 October, 2025.

prorogued on the 9th of September. The prorogation was controversial. When Black Rod⁵¹ came to summon the Commons to hear the Royal Commission for proroguing Parliament, the Speaker stated in the House that:

This is not, however, a normal prorogation. It is not typical. It is not standard. It is one of the longest for decades, and it represents, not just in the minds of many colleagues but for huge numbers of people outside an act of Executive fiat.

Separate legal proceedings to challenge the legality of the prorogation began in the courts of England and Wales, Northern Ireland and Scotland to determine whether the decision to prorogue Parliament was subject to judicial scrutiny. The first question before the courts concerned the justiciability of the prerogative power to prorogue Parliament. That is, could the decision to prorogue be subjected to judicial scrutiny? If found to be justiciable, the second question concerned the legality of the prorogation. Finally, if the advice upon which the decision was based was deemed to be unlawful, what would that mean for the order to prorogue itself, and for the execution of that order?

There were opposing rulings from two different courts. On the 11th of September 2019, the High Court of England and Wales held that the legality of the prorogation was not justiciable in a court of law. That meant that the High Court had determined the question to be beyond the scope of judicial review. On the same day, the Court of Session in Scotland reached the opposite conclusion. It determined that the issue was justiciable. It then concluded that the decision to prorogue Parliament was motivated by an improper purpose. The Court of Session concluded that the prorogation was “unlawful and thus null, and to no effect.”

This led to the matter being referred to the UK Supreme Court. The Court heard appeals from both the decision of the High Court and the Court of Session. On the 24th of September, the UK Supreme Court handed down a unanimous judgment and held that the power to prorogue Parliament is a prerogative power- “a power recognised by the common law and exercised by the Crown... on advice” of the Prime Minister. The Court did not express a view on whether Her Majesty is obliged to act on that advice. The Court then asserted a right to exercise supervisory jurisdiction over decisions of the executive, which was said to have ample judicial precedent. Based on precedents, the Court concluded that it is possible to determine the lawful limits of the exercise of a prerogative power to prorogue Parliament. The Court noted its historical role in protecting “Parliamentary sovereignty from threats posed to it by the use of the prerogative powers” and in doing so have demonstrated that prerogative powers are limited by the principle of Parliamentary sovereignty. The Court went on to hold that:

⁵¹ A Senior parliamentary officer responsible for parliamentary protocol and maintaining order within the upper house of the legislature, similar in function to the sergeant-at-arms in other jurisdictions.

The sovereignty of Parliament would, however, be undermined as the foundational principle of our constitution if the executive could, through the use of the prerogative, prevent Parliament from exercising its legislative authority for as long as it pleased.’

As a result, the Court determined that the power to prorogue cannot be unlimited and must, therefore be subject to judicial review.

On the legality of the prorogation, the Court concluded:

It is impossible for us to conclude, on the evidence which has been put before us, that there was any reason – let alone a good reason – to advise Her Majesty to prorogue Parliament for five weeks, from 9th or 12th September until 14th October. We cannot speculate, in the absence of further evidence, upon what such reasons might have been. It follows that the decision was unlawful.

It suffices therefore to state that despite the traditional position of the UK not to interfere in parliamentary proceedings, not all matters connected with parliament are immune. When decisions by parliamentary officers or bodies have external effects, the courts have occasionally intervened. The UK’s approach to judicial review of parliamentary issues therefore, reflects a careful constitutional balance. While parliamentary sovereignty and privilege remain foundational, the rule of law demands that no public body acts beyond its lawful powers.

3.3.3 South Africa

In South Africa, legislative autonomy is expressly entrenched in the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa by section 57⁵² which provides that the National Assembly may determine and control its internal arrangements, proceedings and procedures, and may make rules and orders concerning its business. A similar provision is found in Section 70 for the National Council of Provinces.⁵³ These provisions establish the legislature’s authority to regulate its internal affairs independently, mirroring the autonomy clauses in Nigeria and India. This autonomy is absolute in relation to regulating internal activities, although, like in other jurisdictions, it remains subject to the overarching principle of constitutional supremacy.⁵⁴

⁵² Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996 www.justice.gov.za/constitution/SACConstitution-web-eng.pdf accessed 20 September, 2025.

⁵³ *ibid.*

⁵⁴ Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996, s 2.

In line with this, both chambers have enacted detailed Rules of the National Assembly⁵⁵ and Rules of the National Council of Provinces,⁵⁶ which regulate the order of business, speaking rights, committees, and disciplinary measures. Like her Nigerian and Indian counterparts, these rules derive directly from constitutional provisions and are binding internally, but they do not supersede the Constitution itself. The South African Constitutional Court has consistently respected legislative autonomy in this regard, intervening only where rules are inconsistent with the Constitution's requirements of legality and accountability.⁵⁷

3.3.4 India

In India, legislative autonomy is expressly provided for under the Constitution of India, 2024. Article 118(1)⁵⁸ stipulates that each House of Parliament may make rules for regulating, subject to the provisions of this Constitution, its procedure and the conduct of its business. A corresponding provision is contained in Article 208⁵⁹ for the State Legislatures. These clauses confer on both Houses of Parliament and State Legislatures the authority to regulate their internal proceedings without external interference. Pursuant to these provisions, the Lok Sabha⁶⁰ and the Rajya Sabha⁶¹ each adopts its Rules of Procedure and Conduct of Business,⁶² while state legislatures enact similar rulebooks. These Standing Orders regulate the legislative calendar, committee structure, questions of order, and sanctions for disorderly conduct. While they are binding within the legislature, they remain subordinate to the Constitution.⁶³ The Supreme Court of India has confirmed this hierarchy, holding in *Raja Ram Pal v. Hon'ble Speaker, Lok Sabha*⁶⁴ that although parliamentary rules are part of legislative privilege, they cannot override constitutional guarantees such as fundamental rights.⁶⁵

⁵⁵See <<https://lawlibrary.org.za/akn/za/act/rules/2016/national-assembly/eng@2020-06-09>> accessed 21 September, 2025.

⁵⁶ See <www.parliament.gov.za/storage/app/media/Rules/NCOP/Rules_of_NCOP_9th_edition.pdf> accessed 21 September, 2025.

⁵⁷ *Doctors for Life International v Speaker of the National Assembly and Others* (CCT12/05) [2006] ZACC 11 <www.saflii.org/za/cases/ZACC/2006/11.html> accessed 21 September, 2025.

⁵⁸ Legislative Department, The Constitution of India, 2024 <<https://legislative.gov.in/constitution-of-india/>> accessed 20 September, 2025.

⁵⁹ *ibid.*

⁶⁰ Upper House; Vajiram Editor, Difference between Lok Sabha and Rajya Sabha, Powers, Members <<https://vajiramandravi.com/upsc-exam/lok-sabha-and-rajya-sabha/>> accessed 21 September, 2025.

⁶¹ Lower House; *ibid.*

⁶² See <https://sansad.in/uploads/LSPP_Questions_Procedure_rules_2c7312313c.pdf?updated_at=2022-09-14T06:16:54.310Z>; See also <https://cms.rajyasabha.nic.in/UploadedFiles/LegislativeSection/LegislativeRules/English_2052022english_3092021rules_pro.pdf> accessed 21 September, 2025.

⁶³ Gajanan Waghmode, 'Case Analysis: Minerva Mills Ltd & Ors. vs. Union Of India & Ors' (2023) (3) (3) Indian Journal of Integrated Research in Law <<https://ijirl.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/CASE-ANALYSIS-MINERVA-MILLS-LTD-ORS.-VS-UNION-OF-INDIA-ORS.pdf>> accessed 21 September, 2025.

⁶⁴ (2007); Neelam Yadav, 'Raja Ram Pal v. Hon'ble Speaker, Lok Sabha (2007)' *iPleaders* (India, 7 September, 2024) <<https://blog.ipleaders.in/raja-ram-pal-vs-honble-speaker-lok-sabha-ors-2007/>> accessed 21 September, 2025.

⁶⁵ *ibid.*

4. JUSTIFICATIONS FOR SUSPENDING LEGISLATORS, THE DEMOCRATIC TENSION, AND JUDICIAL OPINIONS

While such suspensions are typically justified as internal mechanisms to maintain order and uphold the dignity of the legislature, they simultaneously raise serious democratic concerns because they interrupt representation, risk abuse, and can be weaponized for political ends.

4.1 Justifications

In Nigeria, the tension plays out between two constitutional imperatives, which is the autonomy of the legislature to regulate its own proceedings, and the democratic right of representation and fair hearing guaranteed under Sections 36 and 40 of the Nigerian Constitution. These justifications are hereby discussed.

4.1.1 Maintenance of order and decorum

The legislature, like any deliberative body, must maintain discipline to function effectively. Suspension powers serve as a deterrent against disorderly conduct, personal attacks, or contempt of parliamentary rules. From this perspective, suspension operates as a disciplinary mechanism, a means of ensuring that members observe the rules and norms necessary for productive debate and decision-making. Without such powers, debates could easily degenerate into chaos, undermining the integrity of legislative proceedings. This is because contemptuous language, disruptive behaviour, or defiance of the authority of the presiding officer by any legislator can undermine the dignity of the House and erode public confidence in the institution. Maintaining order and decorum therefore provides a legitimate institutional justification for suspension, but one that must be tempered by democratic accountability and constitutional safeguards to prevent abuse, and ensure that the legislature remains both disciplined and representative.

4.1.2 Protection of institutional integrity

Another major justification for the power of the legislature to suspend its members is the need to protect its institutional integrity. The legislature is not merely a gathering of individual politicians, it is a constitutional organ of state entrusted with law-making, oversight, and representative functions that are central to democratic governance. To discharge these functions effectively, the institution must command public respect, legitimacy, and internal coherence. By disciplining errant members (and in this case, through suspensions), the legislature preserves public confidence in its processes.

4.1.3 Enforcement of ethical standards

Every legislative body operates not only on procedural rules, but also on a framework of ethical norms that safeguard public trust in the integrity of governance. Where a member engages in conduct deemed unethical or corrupt, temporary suspension is considered a

corrective measure. Suspension in this context therefore, functions as a disciplinary and corrective tool for enforcing the legislature's code of conduct and ensuring that members uphold the ethical values expected of public office holders. It serves both a deterrent and restorative purpose, deterring misconduct among legislators while preserving public confidence in the commitment of the legislature towards probity, accountability, and good governance.

4.1.4 Expression of legislative autonomy

As stated earlier, section 60 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria empowers each House of the National Assembly to regulate its own procedure. The same applies to State Houses of Assembly through equivalent constitutional provisions and standing orders. Suspension powers are thus defended as part of the internal sovereignty of the legislature, being the right to govern its own affairs without interference.

4.2 The democratic tension

Despite these justifications, suspending an elected representative inevitably strikes at the heart of democracy. Consequently, the following tensions emerge:

4.2.1 Conflict with the right to representation

When legislators are suspended, their constituents lose representation. The punishment imposed on the member becomes, in effect, a penalty on the electorate, a contradiction of democratic equality and popular sovereignty. The Nigerian courts have recognised this, noting that long suspensions disenfranchise constituents and subvert the very purpose of democratic elections. A plethora of Nigerian cases have highlighted the position of the judiciary on this subject.

In the case of *The President of the Senate of The FRN & Ors v Ndume*,⁶⁶ Senator Ali Ndume challenged his suspension by the Senate for a period of 90 legislative days. The Senate had relied on its Standing Orders to suspend the Distinguished Senator as a disciplinary measure. Ndume contended that the action was unconstitutional because it violated his freedom of expression, his right to a fair hearing, and denied his constituents their right to representation in the National Assembly. The Federal High Court agreed with Ndume, holding that although the Senate possesses disciplinary powers, such powers are not absolute. The court reasoned that the suspension of a legislator, particularly for an extended period, effectively silences the constituency that elected him, thereby undermining the principle of democratic representation. It further stressed that legislative rules made pursuant to Section 60 cannot override constitutional guarantees.

In the year 2012, the Bauchi State House of Assembly suspended Hon. Rifkatu Samson Danna indefinitely for voicing out her peoples' opposition to the 'unconstitutional' transfer of the headquarters of Tafawa Balewa Local Government Area

⁶⁶ (2022) LPELR-57712(CA).

from Tafawa Balewa town.⁶⁷ During a debate on the proposed relocation of Tafawa Balewa Local Government headquarters from Tafawa Balewa to Bununu, Danna was the lone voice, explaining that the headquarters of local governments listed in the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria could not be changed without constitutional alteration. While making her point, Hon. Danna said the unanimous and hurried manner in which the decision was reached suggested that there must have been a meeting on the matter to which she was not privy. Despite her apologies, a report of the House Committee on Anti-Corruption, Ethics and Privileges found her remarks during a parliamentary session “repugnant, and quite derogatory.” An investigating House Committee recommended that she should either be suspended indefinitely or be issued a letter of warning. The House chose the former. She sued the House at the Bauchi State High Court. The Court declared the indefinite suspension illegal, unconstitutional, and restored her seat. The House appealed but the Court of Appeal also ruled in Danna’s favour. The House also approached the Supreme Court for an order staying the execution of the Appeal Court judgment that reinstated Danna, but the apex court declined.⁶⁸

In *Dino and 4 others v The Speaker, House of Representatives and 2 others*,⁶⁹ Hon. Dino Melaye and other members of the House of Representatives (the “progressives”) were indefinitely suspended following their exposure of allegations of corruption involving the leadership of the House. The suspension was said to have been passed without affording them a hearing and was accompanied by physical ejection from the chamber.⁷⁰ The Plaintiffs challenged their suspension at the Federal High Court, Abuja, contending that it violated section 68 of the 1999 Constitution (right to hold office until properly vacated), section 36 (fair hearing), their freedom of expression, as well as the rights of their constituents to representation. The House relied on the Legislative Houses (Powers and Privileges) Act and its Standing Orders to justify its action, and further argued that the courts lacked jurisdiction because the matter concerned the internal affairs of the legislature.⁷¹

The court rejected these arguments, and held that legislative powers under section 60 of the Constitution are subject to the Constitution, and that the courts retain jurisdiction where constitutional provisions or fundamental rights are infringed. The court found that the suspension of the legislators for the remainder of the legislative year was unlawful because the House Rules only permitted suspensions not exceeding 14

⁶⁷ ‘Bauchi High Court reinstates suspended legislator, Danna’ *Vanguard* (Nigeria, 31st May, 2013) <www.vanguardngr.com/2013/05/bauchi-high-court-reinstates-suspended-legislator-danna/> accessed on the 22 January, 2023

⁶⁸ *ibid*

⁶⁹ Suit No FHC/ABJ/CS/460/ (FHC, 2 December, 2010).

⁷⁰ C. Anagbogu, ‘Legislative Immunity in Nigeria: Case Review of Dino Melaye and 4 others V. The Speaker, House of Representatives and 2 others’ (2013) (1) (1) *Journal of Current Issues in Nigerian Law* <<https://journals.ezenwaohaetorc.org/index.php/JOCINL/article/view/2068>> accessed 21 September, 2025.

⁷¹ *ibid*.

legislative days.⁷² It also held that the indefinite suspension without fair hearing violated Section 36 of the Constitution and Article 7 of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights. Consequently, the Court declared the suspension illegal, null, and void, affirming that while legislative houses may discipline their members, such powers must be exercised within the bounds of the Constitution.⁷³ The decision, like in Ndume's case, reinforced the principle that disciplinary autonomy cannot be used to disenfranchise the people through excessive or unconstitutional suspensions.

4.2.2 Risk of political weaponization

Suspension powers have often, allegedly been used to silence dissent or punish opposition members. This converts a legitimate disciplinary tool into a partisan instrument, eroding the legislature's role as a pluralistic arena of debate. Several Nigerian cases, including the aforementioned Ali Ndume case demonstrate how disciplinary powers have been contested as unconstitutional when seemingly used arbitrarily. From the way the Standing Rules of legislative Houses are couched however, specifically in the justification of its power to regulate its own proceedings, the acts of arbitrariness and high handedness once a clique of Tyrants desire to suspend a member would remain a recurring decimal.

4.2.3 Violation of fair hearing

Many suspensions are executed without proper notice or an opportunity for defence, contrary to Section 36(1) of the Nigerian Constitution, which guarantees a fair hearing before any determination of civil rights. Courts have repeatedly held that due process must be observed even in internal parliamentary disciplinary actions. While the legislative houses have always maintained their right to mete these punishments out based on their constitutional rights, there are counter arguments to the effect that it is unconstitutional for any legislative chamber to suspend or sack a member. Mr. Femi Falana, Senior Advocate of Nigeria, a Nigerian human rights lawyer posits that only a competent court of law can suspend or remove a member of the legislature whether at local, state or federal government level. According to him, "it is only a court of law or the constituency that elected them that can order the removal or suspension of their representative."⁷⁴ Lending his voice and reiterating his position that no legislative house can suspend a lawmaker when Senator Ndume was suspended, Femi Falana described it as the height of all illegalities.⁷⁵

⁷² *Ibid.*

⁷³ *Ibid.*

⁷⁴ 'No legislative Chamber has power to suspend or remove' *The Cable* (Nigeria, 19th April, 2018) <www.thecable.ng/falana-says-legislature-has-no-power-to-suspend-any-member> accessed on 7 February, 2023.

⁷⁵ 'Falana: Suspension of Senator Ndume illegal', *ThisDay* (Nigeria) <www.pressreader.com/nigeria/thisday/20170330/281986082394515> accessed on 7 February, 2023.

4.2.4 Disproportionality and abuse of duration of suspensions

Where suspensions are excessive (e.g. 180 legislative days), courts have ruled such as unconstitutional for being disproportionate.⁷⁶ A short suspension (e.g., for a few sitting days) may be reasonable, but an extended one effectively functions as expulsion without due process. Further compounding this are the instances of disproportionate length of days of suspensions. Different legislative houses seem to determine the number of days a legislator is suspended, according to their respective whims and caprices. In the Delta State House of Assembly (DTHA) for instance, Hon. Olise Imegwu was suspended from the DTHA for three months in the first instance on the 23rd of February 2010,⁷⁷ Hon. Rufus Akpodiete was suspended indefinitely on the 5th of March, 2012;⁷⁸ Hon. Izeze Rume Yakubu Reuben was suspended from the services of the DTHA for three months on the 7th of June 2016;⁷⁹ while Hon. Monday Igbuya was suspended from the House for three months on the 11th of May 2017.⁸⁰ In 2017, the previously suspended Hon. Izeze Rume Yakubu Reuben was again suspended from the DTHA for three months.⁸¹

These disparities in the length of suspensions happened due primarily to the fact that the suspensions were not determined by any of the provisions of the Standing Rules of the Delta State House of Assembly, because no such provisions regarding the durations exercised exist in the House Rules. This further entrenches the argument that legislative houses arbitrarily use their constitutional rights to regulate their own proceedings.

4.2.5 Judicial oversight, and legislative privilege

Judicial oversight is the constitutional power and duty of the courts to interpret the law and review the actions of other organs of government to ensure conformity with the Constitution. Under Section 6(6)(b) of the Nigerian Constitution, judicial powers extend to all matters between persons, or between government authorities, concerning the determination of rights and obligations. The judiciary therefore, acts as the guardian of the Constitution, ensuring that no branch exceeds its lawful limits, including the

⁷⁶ Ameh Ochojila, 'Legislative Suspensions: Why Practice may be Unconstitutional' *TheGuardian*, (Nigeria, October 15, 2024) <<https://guardian.ng/features/law/legislative-suspensions-why-practice-may-be-unconstitutional/>> accessed 11th November, 2025.

⁷⁷ Austin Ogwuda, 'Delta House Suspends Ex-Speaker over Budget' *Vanguard* (Nigeria, February 24th, 2010) <www.vanguardngr.com/2010/02/delta-house-suspends-ex-speaker-over-budget/> accessed 11 November, 2025.

⁷⁸ 'Delta Assembly Suspends Legislator **As Uduaghan Charges DESOPADEC On Project Monitoring' *Blank News Online* (Nigeria, March 6, 2013) <<https://blanknewsonline.wordpress.com/2013/03/06/delta-assembly-suspends-member-legislator-as-uduaghan-charges-desopadec-on-project-monitoring/>> accessed 11 November, 2025.

⁷⁹ 'Delta Assembly Recalls Suspended Member, Izeze' *The Dream Daily* (Nigeria, July 27, 2016) <www.thedreamdaily.com/delta-assembly-recalls-suspended-member-izeze/> accessed 11 November, 2025.

⁸⁰ Festus Ahon, 'Delta Assembly slams 3 months suspension on erstwhile Speaker, Igbuya' *Vanguard* (Nigeria, September 26, 2018) <<https://www.vanguardngr.com/2018/09/delta-assembly-slams-3-months-suspension-on-erstwhile-speaker-igbuya/>> accessed 11 November, 2025.

⁸¹ Egbonimali Shedrack, 'Why Delta Assembly Suspended Reuben Izeze' *Delta Decides* (Nigeria, September 28, 2017) <https://web.facebook.com/groups/deltadecides2015/posts/1258308414315949/?_rdc=1&_rdr> accessed 11 November, 2025.

legislature. Despite this clear provision, there has been a simmering tension between these two concepts. The Nigerian judiciary has however, been consistent with its recognition of legislative autonomy, but has persistently stated that it will intervene where suspension powers are used in breach of constitutional rights.

The legislature on its part, argues that the internal affairs of the legislature are non-justiciable, invoking the doctrine of separation of powers. The judiciary on the other hand, insists that no authority is above the Constitution, and it must intervene where constitutional rights are infringed, even within internal legislative actions. This tension becomes most visible when courts are asked to review disciplinary actions, suspensions, or internal decisions of the legislature, raising the question- “where does legislative privilege end, and judicial oversight begins”? The conflict arises because both powers legislative autonomy and judicial review are constitutionally grounded. Hence, the tension is not about hostility between institutions, but about defining constitutional boundaries in a democracy that values both autonomy and accountability. In order to consolidate its position, Nigerian courts have developed a balancing approach. The courts generally respect legislative privileges, but will intervene where legislative actions violate the Constitution, breach fundamental rights, are carried out *ultra vires* (beyond lawful authority); or are manifestly unreasonable, disproportionate, or punitive.

Consequently, in *Ovie Omo-Agege v. Senate of the National Assembly*,⁸² the Federal High Court held that while the Senate has the power to regulate its procedures, that power does not extend to suspending a member beyond a reasonable period. The court emphasized that legislative privilege is not absolute, because it must yield to constitutional supremacy and the right to representation. In the aforementioned case of Ali Ndume,⁸³ the Court of Appeal reaffirmed that judicial review applies when suspension violates fundamental rights or exceeds the scope of internal autonomy. The court declared that “the legislature cannot, under the guise of regulating its procedure, punish a member in a manner that silences the voice of his constituents.”

These aforementioned cases notwithstanding, the Nigerian legislative literature was most recently graced with yet another case of disputed suspension of a legislator by the legislature in the case of *Senator Natasha v. The Clerk of the National Assembly of the Federal Republic of Nigeria and 3 Ors.*⁸⁴ On Tuesday, 25 February 2025, Senator Natasha Akpoti-Uduaghan was alleged to have refused to sit on the seat assigned to her during plenary, despite multiple requests from the Minority Leader and other ranking senators. It was further alleged that she spoke without recognition from the President of the Senate, engaged in disruptive behaviour, made disrespectful remarks against Senate leadership, and defied a summons from the Committee on Ethics and Privileges. Based on the Committee’s report finding her guilty of violating Orders 6.1, and 6.2 of the Senate

⁸² Suit No: FHC/ABJ/CS/314/18 (FHC, 10 May, 2010).

⁸³ (2022) LPELR-57712(CA).

⁸⁴ Suit No: FHC/ABJ/CS/384/2025 (10 March, 2025).

Standing Orders 2023, the Senate suspended her for six months on 6th March 2025.⁸⁵ Senator Akpoti-Uduaghan challenged the suspension at the Federal High Court, Abuja, arguing that it was unconstitutional as it infringed her right to fair hearing, her freedom of expression, and the constitutional right of her constituents to representation.

In its decision, the Federal High Court acknowledged the Senate's power to discipline members under its Standing Orders but criticised the six-month suspension of Senator Natasha Akpoti-Uduaghan as excessive and unconstitutional, since it amounted to excluding her for the entire legislative year and thereby undermined her constituents' right to representation. The Court described Section 14(2) of the Legislative Houses (Powers and Privileges) Act, which permits suspension for such period as determined by the House, as overreaching and inconsistent with constitutional guarantees. However, despite these findings, the Court stopped short of issuing a definitive reinstatement order. Instead, it delivered declaratory reliefs and suggested that she should be recalled, leaving the enforcement in limbo. This indecision had immediate consequences because Senator Natasha was physically restricted from accessing the National Assembly complex after the judgment,⁸⁶ and even after serving out the full six-month suspension, continued to be denied entry under the guise of *lis pendens* (sometimes loosely described as *sub judice* in Nigerian legal discourse), with the argument being that the appeal must first be determined before the Distinguished Senator can resume her seat.⁸⁷

This cautious judicial attitude stands in stark contrast with Ndume's case, where the Court of Appeal treated the appeal as academic because the suspension period had already lapsed. The implication is clear, in that, had the Federal High Court in Natasha's case taken a definitive stance, as it did in Ndume, the stalemate, where a legislator is indefinitely barred despite serving her punishment may have been avoided. By refusing to go beyond declaratory reliefs, the court effectively enabled the Senate to frustrate constitutional rights under the cover of procedural technicalities.

The paper therefore criticises the Court's approach as judicial abdication, because while recognising the unconstitutionality of the suspension, it failed to provide an enforceable remedy. This weakens the authority of the judiciary, emboldens the legislature to persist in unconstitutional suspensions, and, most critically, perpetuate the disenfranchisement of constituents who remain unrepresented.

⁸⁵ "Nigerian Senate Frantically Defends Six-Month Suspension Of Senator Natasha Amid Public Backlash", *Sahara Reporters*, (Nigeria, March 8, 2025) <<https://saharareporters.com/2025/03/08/nigerian-senate-frantically-defends-six-month-suspension-senator-natasha-amid-public>> accessed on 11 March, 2025.

⁸⁶ Policy and Legal Advocacy Centre (PLAC), Senator Natasha Akpoti-Uduaghan Barred from National Assembly as Court Order Sparks Political Standoff <<https://placng.org/Legist/senator-natasha-akpoti-uduaghan-barred-from-national-assembly-as-court-order-sparks-political-standoff/>> accessed 21 September, 2025.

⁸⁷ This Day, 'Senate-Akpabio vs Senator Natasha Akpoti-Uduaghan' *ThisDaylive*, (Nigeria, 15 September, 2025) <www.thisdaylive.com/2025/09/16/senate-akpabio-vs-senator-natasha-akpoti-uduaghan/> accessed 21 July, 2025.

Taken together, the case of *Ndume*,⁸⁸ *Dino*,⁸⁹ and *Natasha*⁹⁰ reveal a troubling inconsistency in the judicial handling of legislative suspensions in Nigeria. In *Ndume* and *Dino*, the courts were clear that while the legislature may discipline its members, suspension powers are limited by constitutional guarantees of fair hearing, freedom of expression, and the right of constituents to representation. In both cases, the Federal High Court struck down suspensions that exceeded the scope permitted by the Standing Orders, affirming that legislative autonomy cannot override constitutional supremacy. Yet in *Natasha*'s case, although the Court criticised the six-month suspension as excessive and inconsistent with the Constitution, it stopped short of granting definitive relief. This indecision emboldened the Senate to bar the legislator from the National Assembly even after judgment, and later to prolong her exclusion under the guise of *lis pendens* (or *sub judice*), despite her having served the full suspension. The contrast illustrates a retreat from the robust stance in the *Ndume* and *Dino* cases, and raises serious concerns about judicial resolve in protecting democratic representation. This paper therefore argues that if the court in *Natasha*'s case had taken a categorical position, similar to the approach in *Ndume*, the disenfranchisement of her constituents would likely have been forestalled. It is safe therefore to state that legislative privilege does not grant immunity from judicial review, because autonomy ends where arbitrariness begins.

4.3 Comparative jurisprudence

4.3.1 The United Kingdom

In the United Kingdom, legislative autonomy is underpinned by the doctrine of parliamentary sovereignty and the constitutional settlement established by the Bill of Rights 1689.⁹¹ Article 9 of the Bill of Rights provides that “the freedom of speech and debates or proceedings in Parliament ought not to be impeached or questioned in any court or place out of Parliament.”⁹² This provision has traditionally been interpreted to exclude judicial interference in the internal proceedings of Parliament. The leading case is *Bradlaugh v Gossett*,⁹³ where the court was invited to determine whether Mr. Bradlaugh, an elected Member of Parliament could be prevented by the House of Commons from taking his seat after refusing to take the religious oath required at the time. The court declined jurisdiction, holding that “the House of Commons has the exclusive right to regulate its own internal proceedings,” and that the courts had no

⁸⁸ (2022) LPELR-57712(CA).

⁸⁹ Suit No FHC/ABJ/CS/460/ (FHC, 2 December, 2010).

⁹⁰ Suit No: FHC/ABJ/CS/384/2025 (10 March, 2025).

⁹¹ Erskine May (n 25); <www.parliament.gov.za/storage/app/media/Rules/NCOP/Rules_of_NCOP_9th_edition.pdf> accessed 21 September, 2025.

⁹² *ibid*.

⁹³ *Bradlaugh* (n 48).

authority to interfere.⁹⁴ Thus, even where parliamentary actions arguably affect representation, the judiciary has consistently maintained a hands-off approach, deferring to the absolute autonomy of Parliament in managing its affairs.

The Court recognised that while a resolution of the House of Commons cannot change the law of the land, the House is the absolute judge of its own privileges and internal proceedings.⁹⁵ This position has been reinforced by subsequent decisions,⁹⁶ with UK courts drawing a firm line between matters of internal parliamentary procedure, which are non-justiciable, and matters of statutory or external effect, where limited judicial review may be possible.⁹⁷ Accordingly, unlike Nigeria, where courts have intervened to protect constitutional rights from legislative excess, the United Kingdom preserves the supremacy of parliamentary privilege by excluding judicial scrutiny of suspensions or expulsions imposed by Parliament, thereby undermining the doctrine of checks and balances. It must be noted however, that this holds with the exception of the already discussed cases where the UK Parliament has held that it can intervene in exceptional circumstances.

4.3.2 South Africa

The scope of judicial intervention within the South-African jurisdiction is typified in the decision of the court in the case of the Western Cape High Court in *Economic Freedom Fighters and Others v Chairperson of the Powers and Privileges Committee and others*.⁹⁸ The case concerned the suspension of six Members of the National Assembly for one month following their disruption of the 2023 State of the Nation Address. The Members challenged the disciplinary process and sought an interim interdict preventing the suspension from taking effect. The Court held that, although sections 57 and 70 of the Constitution confer broad powers on Parliament to regulate its internal arrangements, this autonomy does not operate as an absolute shield against judicial scrutiny. The High Court further held that the judiciary may intervene in internal parliamentary disciplinary processes where applicants establish prima facie right, show irreparable harm, and demonstrate that the balance of convenience favours intervention. In other words, judicial review is available, but not automatic.⁹⁹ However, applying these principles, the Court declined to restrain Parliament. It found that the Members had not demonstrated a constitutional infirmity sufficiently grave to justify judicial intrusion into the Assembly's disciplinary domain. The alleged deficiencies in the Rules, such as the absence of detailed

⁹⁴ UK Parliament, Standing Orders <www.parliament.uk/site-information/glossary/standing-orders/> accessed 20th September, 2025.

⁹⁵ *ibid.*

⁹⁶ *British Railways Board v Pickin* [1974] 1 All ER 609; *Prebble v Television New Zealand Ltd* [1995] 1 AC 321.

⁹⁷ *ibid.*

⁹⁸ (23230/23) [2024] ZAWCHC 31 (8 February 2024) <https://www.saflii.org/za/cases/ZAWCHC/2024/31.html#_ftnref9> accessed 15th November, 2025.

⁹⁹ *ibid.*

guidelines on sanctions or time-limits did not, in the Court's view, amount to violations of legality or procedural fairness. Nor did the temporary suspension constitute irreparable harm, despite its effect on constituency representation. Accordingly, the suspension was allowed to stand.

This case is instructive for two reasons. It confirms that South African Courts can intervene where internal disciplinary measures infringe constitutional rights or breach the principle of legality. Legislative autonomy is therefore subject to constitutional supremacy. It also shows that South African Courts adopt a restrained, deferential posture, intervening only where the constitutional threshold is clearly met. Suspensions that are temporary, proportionate, and procedurally regular will not ordinarily be disturbed. Thus, South Africa represents a middle ground in comparative jurisprudence: unlike the United Kingdom, where internal parliamentary discipline is insulated from review, South Africa recognises judicial authority to examine legislative sanctions, but exercises that authority sparingly. The effect is a balanced model in which autonomy is respected, yet constitutionality remains the ultimate standard. As earlier discussed, legislative autonomy is expressly entrenched in the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa.¹⁰⁰ Section 57 empowers the National Assembly to determine and control its internal arrangements, proceedings and procedures, while section 70 makes similar provision for the National Council of Provinces. These provisions mirror the autonomy clauses in Nigeria and India, granting legislatures wide latitude to regulate their own affairs.

Previously, in *Mazibuko v Sisulu and Another*,¹⁰¹ the court was asked to compel the Speaker of the National Assembly to schedule a motion of no confidence in the President. While affirming that parliament enjoys autonomy over its scheduling and rules, the Court stressed that such autonomy must be exercised in a manner consistent with constitutional democracy and accountability. In other words, judicial review remains available where legislative inaction or procedure undermines constitutional rights or democratic principles. Thus, unlike in other already discussed jurisdictions where courts refrain from questioning parliamentary procedure, South Africa represents a middle ground, in that legislative autonomy is respected, but is not insulated from constitutional supremacy. This is because courts retain the authority to ensure that legislatures act within the framework of participatory democracy and accountability required by the Constitution.

4.3.3 India

As earlier discussed, the Indian Constitution entrenches legislative autonomy through Articles 105 and 118, which confer parliamentary privileges and empower each House to regulate its procedure. Article 194 makes parallel provision for State Legislatures. These

¹⁰⁰ 1996 Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, ss 57 and 70 <<https://www.justice.gov.za/constitution/SACConstitution-web-eng.pdf>> accessed 20th September, 2025.

¹⁰¹ 2013 (6) SA 249 (CC).

clauses give legislative bodies broad authority to manage their own internal affairs, including the power to discipline members. The Supreme Court of India has, however, consistently affirmed that this autonomy is subject to constitutional supremacy.

Here, the cases of *Raja Ram Pal v Hon'ble Speaker, Lok Sabha*¹⁰² and *Kihoto Hollohan v Zachillhu*¹⁰³ are instructive. In *Kihoto Hollohan v Zachillhu*,¹⁰⁴ the court examined the validity of the Tenth Schedule which introduced the anti-defection law. While the court upheld the Schedule as constitutional, it struck down Paragraph 7 which sought to exclude judicial review, as violative of the basic structure doctrine. The Court held that decisions of the Speaker under the anti-defection law were justiciable and may be reviewed on grounds of mala fides, perversity, or violation of constitutional mandates.¹⁰⁵ This case firmly established that legislative autonomy cannot operate as an ouster of judicial authority.

The principle was deepened in *Raja Ram Pal v Hon'ble Speaker, Lok Sabha*,¹⁰⁶ arising from the “cash-for-questions” scandal. Parliament had expelled Members for accepting bribes in exchange for raising questions in the House. The Supreme Court upheld parliament’s power of expulsion as an aspect of its privileges, but stressed that such powers must operate within the limits of the Constitution. It declared that judicial review extends even to questions of parliamentary privilege, although exercised with restraint, and that expulsions or suspensions shall be struck down if shown to be illegal, irrational, mala fide, or inconsistent with constitutional guarantees.¹⁰⁷ The Court emphasised that parliamentary privilege cannot be a licence for arbitrary action and is subject to the basic structure of the Constitution, which includes democracy, the rule of law, and judicial review.¹⁰⁸

Taken together, the cases of *Kihoto Hollohan* and *Raja Ram Pal* illustrate India’s balanced approach that legislatures enjoy wide powers to regulate and discipline themselves, but these powers remain subordinate to the Constitution. Unlike the United Kingdom, where judicial restraint excludes scrutiny of internal proceedings, Indian Courts have asserted their role as ultimate guardians of constitutional supremacy. The result is a system where suspension or expulsion may be validly imposed, but never beyond the reach of judicial review.

¹⁰² (2007).

¹⁰³ iPleaders, *Kihoto Hollohan v Zachillhu* (1993) *iPleaders* Friday 27 June, 2025 <https://blog.ipleaders.in/kihoto-hollohan-vs-zachillhu-1993/> accessed 21 September, 2025.

¹⁰⁴ *ibid.*

¹⁰⁵ *ibid.*

¹⁰⁶ iPleaders, *Kihoto Hollohan v Zachillhu* (1993) *iPleaders* Friday 27 June, 2025 <https://blog.ipleaders.in/kihoto-hollohan-vs-zachillhu-1993/> accessed 21 September, 2025.

¹⁰⁷ 2007); Neelam Yadev, ‘Raja Ram Pal v. Hon’ble Speaker, Lok Sabha (2007)’ *iPleaders* Saturday 7 September, 2024 <<https://blog.ipleaders.in/raja-ram-pal-vs-honble-speaker-lok-sabha-ors-2007/>> accessed 21st September, 2025.

¹⁰⁸ *ibid.*

A comparative reading of Nigeria, the United Kingdom, India, and South Africa therefore, reveals an interesting, and divergent spectrum of judicial attitudes toward legislative autonomy and disciplinary powers. At one end lies the United Kingdom, where the doctrine of parliamentary sovereignty and Article 9 of the Bill of Rights 1689 insulates internal parliamentary proceedings from judicial scrutiny, (albeit with the exceptions already discussed) reflecting near-total judicial restraint. At the other end is Nigeria, where courts have intervened robustly in cases such as *Ndume*¹⁰⁹ and *Dino*¹¹⁰ to invalidate unconstitutional suspensions, but with troubling inconsistency, as shown by the indecision in *Natasha*.¹¹¹ Between these poles are India and South Africa, both of which adopt a more balanced model, that their constitutions entrench legislative autonomy, yet the courts affirm that such autonomy is subject to constitutional supremacy. In India, *Kihoto Hollohan*¹¹² and *Raja Ram Pal*¹¹³ established that even parliamentary privileges are justiciable when they violate the basic structure of the Constitution. In South Africa, *Doctors for Life*¹¹⁴ and *Mazibuko*¹¹⁵ demonstrate that while legislatures may regulate their own proceedings, courts will intervene where constitutional obligations, such as public participation, accountability, or proportionality, are undermined.

Together, these jurisdictions highlight the central tension between respecting legislative self-regulation and safeguarding constitutional rights, with Nigeria's inconsistency standing out as a cautionary example of what judicial hesitation or overreach can amount to. Thus, even globally, the trend is toward measured judicial intervention, not to control legislative processes, but to ensure constitutional compliance.

5. FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The principle of legislative autonomy occupies a central place in constitutional democracies. It embodies the idea that a legislature, as an independent arm of government, must possess the freedom to regulate its own proceedings, discipline its members, and safeguard its institutional integrity without interference from the executive or judiciary. This autonomy ensures that the legislative process remains free from external intimidation or influence, thereby preserving the doctrine of separation of powers and protecting democratic deliberation. Yet, this same autonomy gives rise to a complex and persistent dilemma, and in essence, the paradox of autonomy. While autonomy is designed to preserve the legislature's independence and dignity, it simultaneously creates the possibility of institutional excess and abuse of power. When

¹⁰⁹ (2022) LPELR-57712(CA).

¹¹⁰ Suit No FHC/ABJ/CS/460/ (FHC, 2 December, 2010).

¹¹¹ Suit No: FHC/ABJ/CS/384/2025 (10 March, 2025).

¹¹² iPleaders, *Kihoto Hollohan v Zachillhu* (1993) *iPleaders* Friday 27 June, 2025 <https://blog.ipleaders.in/kihoto-hollohan-vs-zachillhu-1993/> accessed 21 September, 2025.

¹¹³ *Raja Ram Pal v Hon'ble Speaker, Lok Sabha* (2007).

¹¹⁴ *Doctors for Life International* (n 55).

¹¹⁵ *Mazibuko* (n 97).

disciplinary or suspension powers are exercised arbitrarily or for partisan motives, autonomy ceases to serve democracy and begins to subvert the very constitutional values it was meant to protect.

This paper finds that suspension powers are justifiable but susceptible to abuse. The research identifies that the power to suspend legislators is grounded in legitimate institutional objectives such as maintenance of order and decorum, protection of institutional integrity, and enforcement of ethical standards. However, in practice, these justifications are often stretched or politicised, leading to arbitrary or excessive suspensions that undermine the representational rights of constituents and the plural character of the legislature. The paper also finds that suspensions affect the core of democratic representation because findings reveal that the suspension of a legislator extends beyond personal discipline, it deprives constituents of representation, distorting the balance of voices within the legislature and diminishing the democratic ideal of popular participation. Prolonged or indefinite suspensions, therefore, constitute a collective punishment of the electorate, which contradicts the foundational principles of representative democracy.

Drawing from comparative trends, the paper equally finds that judicial oversight is a necessary constitutional check on the activities of the legislature. Judicial intervention does not erode legislative autonomy but rather preserves it within lawful limits, ensuring that autonomy does not degenerate into impunity. The study also finds that the autonomy granted to legislatures to safeguard their independence can paradoxically become the basis for internal authoritarianism, and subjugations. When suspension powers are used to silence dissent or opposition, autonomy becomes a tool of exclusion rather than a protector of institutional integrity. The study thus underscores the paradox of legislative autonomy, that the legislature's independence, although vital, must operate within constitutional limits. Absolute autonomy contradicts the spirit of constitutionalism and invites abuse. True institutional integrity is not secured through unrestrained privilege but through the consistent alignment of legislative self-regulation with the principles of justice, fairness, and the rule of law. Judicial oversight, therefore, becomes an indispensable constitutional safeguard, one that does not erode legislative privilege but ensures its legitimate and proportionate use. In modern constitutional democracies, including Nigeria, the task is to strike a careful balance between legislative self-governance and constitutional accountability, a balance that preserves both the dignity of the legislature and the democratic rights of the people it represents.

Procedural deficiencies, the paper finds, encourages the misuse of disciplinary powers. The research reveals that in many legislatures, particularly in Nigeria, the absence of clear procedural safeguards, codified disciplinary frameworks, and impartial ethics committees creates fertile ground for the misuse of suspension powers. Political majorities often dominate disciplinary proceedings, undermining fairness and eroding public confidence in legislative institutions.

Consequently, this paper recommends a codification of disciplinary procedures in the Rules of legislative houses, clearly specifying the scope, duration, grounds, and procedures for the suspension of members. This codification should ensure transparency, due process, and proportionality, specifying the maximum duration and conditions under which suspension may occur.

The paper further recommends an institutionalization of independent Ethics and Disciplinary Committees that are non-partisan, and responsible for investigating alleged misconduct. This non-partisan nature can be achieved by ensuring that the composition of the Committee reflects party balance and include procedural safeguards to prevent partisan manipulation. It is also recommended that internal accountability mechanisms are promoted, and legislative houses should adopt mechanisms for internal appeal or review of disciplinary decisions to allow reconsideration before external judicial intervention. This strengthens self-regulation while preserving fairness. There should also be continuous capacity building for legislators and the public on the limits of legislative privileges, and the importance of democratic accountability because educated understanding reduces misuse and enhances the legitimacy of legislative processes.

Finally, in order to forestall the negative effects, the suspension of legislators has on constituent members, this paper recommends an alternative punishment in the nature of fines for such legislators. This sort of punishment only affects the legislator directly, and does not affect the members of the legislator's constituency. Fines collected from such legislators should be put in a dedicated Fund for either a general or specific use of the concerned legislative house.

6. CONCLUSION

A legislature must be free to act as master of its own house, but it must also remain subject to the higher principles of representation, justice, and the rule of law. If autonomy is interpreted as absolute immunity from external scrutiny, it risks becoming a cloak for impunity, allowing majorities to silence minorities or exclude dissenting members under the guise of preserving order or enforcing ethics. Conversely, excessive judicial intrusion into legislative affairs could undermine legislative privilege and weaken the balance of powers. The challenge, therefore, lies in reconciling autonomy with accountability. Modern constitutional jurisprudence recognises that legislative self-regulation cannot stand above constitutional norms.

This paper concludes by stating that the legitimacy of legislative autonomy depends not on insulation from review, but on responsible, constitutionally guided exercise of disciplinary powers. As a result, the suspension of legislators must remain a measure of last resort, aimed not at silencing opposition or consolidating political power, but at preserving the integrity and credibility of the legislature as the foremost guardian of democratic representation.